

THE CONCEPT OF "ADVERTISING" AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN RAISING SOCIAL AWARENESS

Khalikulova Musharraf

Master student, Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan
mashakhalikulovagmail.com

Scientific advisor: **Yugay Yevgeniya**,
Doctor of philosophy, teacher of NSPI, Uzbekistan

Abstract: *This article is devoted to the description of the social advertising and its importance in communication as material for language learning. Moreover, the meaning of the concept of "advertising", the text of the advertisement and its classification are discussed.*

Key words: *advertising, social advertisement, national stereotype, national character, verbal and non-verbal means, social behavior, social involvement.*

Аннотация: *Статья посвящена описанию социальной рекламы и ее сущности, ее значения в общении как материала для изучения языка. Кроме того, обсуждается значение понятия «реклама», текст рекламы и ее классификация.*

Ключевые слова: *реклама, социальная реклама, национальный стереотип, национальный характер, вербальные и невербальные средства, социальное поведение, социальная вовлеченность.*

INTRODUCTION. In today's globalization era, the influence of mass media on humanity is increasing significantly. Advertising serves as a convenient resource in all fields, even in language learning. Because advertising text is usually written in easy language without using complex grammatical structures.

One of the most widespread and all-pervasive types of communication in the modern world is advertising. Consumers are exposed to advertising messages via newspapers, magazines, radio, television, and the internet. Although the main purpose of advertising for small businesses is to inform consumers about their goods and services, advertising techniques often serve to bring attention to societal issues. Strong visuals, emotional music, and well written content can arouse attitudes in viewers and encourage social change.

It should be noted that a lot of information has been collected due to the researches about the concept of "advertising", its emergence, meaning and developing steps. The term "advertising" comes from the Latin word "reklamo" - "to shout", "and in modern language it means to deliver information about a certain product to the public.

Advertising is "... information about goods and services in order to inform customers about them, to create or increase their demand and need" [Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language, 373-374 b].

LITERATURE REVIEW. Advertising was significant in ancient times according to this current meaning. In actuality, this word first appeared in our language in the 1850s. However, the earliest types of advertising originated in ancient nations and are now kept in the British Museum. As an example, an Egyptian papyrus advertisement for the sale of a slave can be brought. In the inscription about the slave being sold, there are records that described the peculiarities of the slave. And the owners wrote them to the customers in order to encourage buying.

Additionally, there were advertisements at the time of ancient Greece and Rome, like wooden boards, copper scraps, and bone carvings.

Although advertising has rich historical roots in Uzbekistan, this field remained out of the scientific community's attention until independence. After independence, a number of scientific research works on advertising were carried out. For example, A.A.Azlarova studied the effectiveness of advertisements from the point of view of marketing, while L.I.Karimova studied social psychological and ethnopsychological aspects of advertisements. K.V.Mosin examined aspects of the effect of advertising on the moral and moral education of a person. In recent years, a lot of work has been done to develop the advertising industry. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Advertising" was adopted on June 7, 2022 in order to ensure the legal basis for creating and distributing advertising.

Also S.V. Karpova, who conducted modern scientific research ("International Advertising Work" in Russian), Yu.S.Bernadskaya and S.S. Marochkina, L.F. Smotrovalar ("Basics of advertising"), M. Rashidova ("Methodology of advertising"), L.D. In the works of Stolyarenko ("Fundamentals of Psychology" in Russian), E. Utkin, A. Kachetkova ("Advertising Work" in Russian) the necessary information on the subject is thoroughly analyzed.

DISCUSSION. Advertisements differ from each other according to the principle of creation, for example, marketing, communicative, educational, economic, social advertising, etc.

Nowadays, various information attacks are increasing all over the world. For this reason, the demand for social advertisements that illuminate the issues in society and

are aimed at solving them is increasing more and more. This type of advertising is mainly devoted to highlighting and raising awareness of social protection motives in the country. Examples of this type of advertising include posters that cover the topics of harmful habits, environmental problems, and Internet addiction and like these.

The most correct and complete concept of social advertising was quoted by S. P. Grishaev. He said that social advertising is information directed to an unlimited number of people in any form and using any means, aimed at achieving charitable and other socially useful goals, as well as ensuring the interests of the state.

The emergence of social advertising dates back to 1906. At that time, advertisements were designed to attract American citizens to the defense. During the First World War, the field of social advertising rapidly developed with the establishment of the "Committee on Public Information" to inform the population about the aims and causes of the war. Afterwards, the invention of the camera by Jacques Louis Daguerre in 1839 caused to make advertising more reliable and memorable with visual effects.

In the Soviet period, social advertising had a political character, it is not very diverse, it is characterized by the fact that it is prepared in a political spirit. At that time, social advertising was used to perform information, image and communication functions. Basically, social advertisements were created with a special place for promotion and education tasks.

Since the 20s, posters depicting the main themes of war, the fight against dissidents, hunger, and the ideas of communism have been displayed.

At the end of the 50s, political coverage began, and today the direction of social advertising is changing and expanding in terms of content. For example, new topics such as healthy lifestyle, physical education and sports have appeared.

Special attention should be paid to the following aspects of social advertising:

- Controls their social behavior by influencing the mass audience;
- If it is positively received by the audience, the advertisement increases the reputation of the producers and does not require any financial income in the distribution process.

Social issue ads aim to influence perceptions, encourage action, or increase awareness of a particular public issue. Although they provide a number of difficulties and ethical issues, they can be efficient means of social change. There are numerous reasons to contribute the advertisement success.

The following are some of its advantages:

- It enhances people's social and cultural behaviour.
- It's a tool that can be applied to improve societal welfare.
- It raises people's standard of living financially.

- It gives them access to chances to improve their life and find work.
- It offers them fresh avenues for fulfilment.
- Publicly acceptable advertising benefits society as a whole.
- As society ideals change, so should advertising.
- It provides housewives with information on things that can lessen their drudgery. Products like cooking gas, washing machines, mixers, grinders, etc. are advertised in this way.
- It promotes family planning, something the country desperately needs.
- It raises awareness of a variety of illnesses, including AIDS and cancer.
- It informs them of the remedies available for certain conditions.

Focusing the person's attention on advertising, stimulating his abilities in the field of perception is recognized as an individual process in psychology.

Social advertising will be effective if it matches the inner mental state of the person and the real needs in it. In this case, the effectiveness is evaluated by the extent to which it is adapted to the way of life of the population, national-cultural traditions, traditions and values. In other words, the success of advertising depends on how adopted the given information is to national stereotypes and national character qualities. Advertisements have a high psychological impact in maintaining a healthy environment in society, increasing people's sense of self-confidence, and creating a healthy attitude towards life. Advertisements that express the lifestyle and character of people are more positively received. Because any advertisement is based on a system of psychological laws. Advertising information is presented in a combination of verbal and non-verbal means, musical texts, short and long, various images and drawings. In the process of understanding advertising, reacting to it allows a person to freely assess social reality, demonstrate social behavior skills, and awaken a sense of social involvement.

According to the content of social advertising, the following main types can be mentioned:

a) Advertisements of national holidays, traditions and values;

This type of advertising conveys a small message or announcement to the public about upcoming national and international holidays, various national traditions.

b) Advertisements about various projects, events, conferences or programs of non-profit organizations;

Examples of such advertisements include advertising of the state program for sorting waste for recycling among citizens, and the "Young Reader" project to interest young people in reading books. Information about charity fundraising events is also conveyed using this type of advertisement.

c) Informational and educational advertisements, e.g.

- advertising about keeping clean - promotes cleanliness and public order in society;
- an advertisement depicting the care of children - attracting the attention of parents to raising their children.

In order to influence public attitude towards a certain issue, advertisement producers usually take into consideration following linguistic constructions.

Humor is a tactic used in social advertising campaigns to grab attention and start a conversation. Although it can be risky, humor can also be beneficial if used correctly.

Using storytelling to engage an audience, convey a message, or motivate action is a useful tactic used in advertising campaigns aimed at social causes. Using stories to engage your audience on a personal and emotional level can be very effective.

The next tactic for social advertising campaigns is to build trust, establish legitimacy, authority or trust through *credibility*. You can build credibility by presenting data, figures, evidence or recommendations from reliable sources. For example, the Truth campaign used legitimacy to expose the deceit and fraud of the tobacco industry and discourage youth smoking. The campaign exposed the negative impact of smoking and the dishonest business practices of tobacco companies by presenting data, statistics and commentary from industry documents and experts.

Using ethics is powerful strategy to appeal to the values, morals, or principles of the audience. Ethics can be a powerful way to persuade an audience to support a cause, but it can also be controversial or problematic. For example, the PETA campaign used ethics to advocate for animal rights and to criticize animal cruelty and exploitation. The campaign used graphic images, shocking slogans and celebrity endorsements to expose cruelty and violence in the meat, fur and leather industries. The campaign received a lot of attention, but also faced criticism and backlash for being insensitive, offensive, or misleading.

CONCLUSION. To conclude, the study of advertising texts requires a different approach in linguistics. The success of advertising is determined by the correct choice of language units used in it. Because presenting the advantages of the advertised product to the consumer in an understandable language and form helps to increase the effectiveness of advertising. The most effective instrument available to advertisers for conveying their message is language. An effective use of language can distinguish between a poor and excellent advertisement. Consequently, language and linguistics play a significant role in the marketing of advertising, their efficacy, and the overall message and goal that advertisers hope to get through to their target audience.

Advertising is becoming an active part of our daily life as a means of influencing social processes, forming a protective shell against various foreign ideas, speeding up the development of society as much as possible.

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